

RepuChain: A Privacy-Preserving Reputation Consensus for Medical IoT Data Formulation

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Abstract—The overall reliability of the Internet of Things (IoT) enabled medical systems to rely on the captured data and associated services. Therefore, it is important to formulate non-malicious and unbiased data for data-driven medical IoT applications. In this paper, we identify the strength of blockchain and smart contracts in consensus-driven malicious data elimination for reliable medical data formulation for decentralized IoT medical services. Our work proposes a novel consensus protocol that leverages the reputation score as a numerical indicator to identify malicious data with privacy-preserved reputation verification for ensured fair and unbiased data formulation. We validated the proposed architecture by implementing an online medical diagnosis use case, and programmatic numerical event-driven simulations. The results reflect that our work outperforms the state-of-the-art by latency improvement (up to 57%) while supporting scalability and improved fairness (up to 97% node utilization in the experiment).

Index Terms—Blockchain, Smart Contract, Privacy, IoT, Consensus

I. INTRODUCTION

The uneven distribution of healthcare services across geographic regions is one of the biggest challenges that remains remote areas underserved without access to medical services. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) -integrated medical services bridge this gap by providing people with seamless access to medical services with advanced information and rapid response. Enabling access to cross-regional, persistent medical services eliminates the digital divide between communities and improves quality of life. With the advancement of mobile communications Beyond 5th Generation (5G) networks, the Internet and the Internet of Things (IoT) are redefining the paradigm of medical ICT services by expanding their capabilities while bridging the gap between human and medical services with mobile-cloud integration for services such as medical diagnosis [1] with wearables [2] for medical diagnosis. However, with the integration of IoT and smart wearable devices, the cloud emerges as an evolving threat landscape with security risks.

Security, scalability, and efficiency are key expectations of production-grade IoT-integrated medical services to support extended scales of the population. Especially in IoT-integrated medical services, it is important to align the principle of “security by design” with compliance to the industry and regulatory priorities such as General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR)

[3], and the Health Information Portability and Accountability Act [4]. In addition, medical IoT-integrated decisions must promise the preservation of sustainability goals with proven efficiency to convince stakeholders [5] in strategic decisions.

Focusing on security aspects, with the centralized architecture for IoT data storage and service invocation, we have identified the critical and life-threatening security risks of cloud-based medical diagnostic systems, including the risk of malicious data injection, tampering and unavailability of services due to malicious attacks. On the other hand, blockchain has become a game changer for medical IoT security with many use cases such as secured medical data management [6], IoT device management [7], and medical diagnosis [8] by incorporating a distributed ledger, decentralized operational capability through smart contracts [9] with cryptographically linked digital ledger and decentralized smart contracts, eliminating single point of failure and ensuring data integrity. Rahman et al. [10] proposed Proof of trust and expertise (PoTE) blockchain platform for electronic medical health record management, however the influence of expertise score significantly affect the fundamental fairness expectations of the decentralized systems by the potential for converging the mining power to a selected group, which will eventually discourage the blockchain members. Dewanagan et al. [11] proposed TempChain, a blockchain-based architecture with proof of work (PoW) consensus for telehealth data sharing. However, PoW demands extensive time and energy for the underlying puzzle-solving components which emerge as uncertainty in real-time healthcare management systems with significant sustainability concerns, which is applicable for [6] too. In addition Proof of Familiarity (PoF) [8] and Proof of Authority (PoA) [7] consensus protocols expose the system into the risk of converging the mining power to a set of nodes, motivated by the reputation scores which are visible to the members and compromising fairness. zkSNARK-based privacy-preserved reputation verification techniques [12] demand extensive network and computational overhead with asymmetric key generation for each proof.

Identifying the significant limitations of recent research in the context of consensus-driven IoT-integrated medical systems, we propose a new reputation-based consensus protocol named RepuChain that provides a smart contract-based platform for in-

tegrating state-of-the-art medical IoT data validation frameworks as smart contracts, leveraging data-quality-based reputation for mining node election, efficiently privacy-preserved reputation score proof, and distinguishing and eliminating malicious data-generating medical IoT nodes with improved fairness. The smart contract-based platform operates with decentralized privacy functions to improve scalability for healthcare medical service functions. Finally, the benefits of the proposed architecture are demonstrated through an end-to-end testbed implementation and a performance evaluation of the results. For privacy-preserved reputation verification to ensure the competition miners cannot see the reputation score of each other, we leveraged BulletProof [13] Zero Knowledge Proof (ZKP) that comprises a three-step approach: (1) *Initialization*, (2) *Pedersen commitment generation*, and (3) *Proof*. The main advantage is BulletProof-based reputation verification does not require a trusted third party and individual key generation for each proof.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides a technical overview of the proposed service architecture and end-to-end operational workflow. Section III presents the testbed implementation and experimental results. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper.

II. PROPOSED REPUCHAIN BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

A. System definition

The IoT-enabled medical ICT services include medical IoT sensors that generate the IoT data with connectivity to the Healthcare Service Providers (HSP), a processing service for the generated data, the application of privacy functions to ensure confidentiality before data storage, a storage service to store the data, and medical services that provide outputs for various scenarios such as patient input and data sharing. For this purposes, we propose consortium blockchain system based on the agreement of predefined HSP nodes as miners. The proposed system has HSP blockchain nodes $HSP = \{HSP_\alpha, HSP_\beta, \dots\}$ and human-connected IoT sensor devices $D = \{D_\alpha, D_\beta, \dots\}$ that are connected to the HSP nodes. The system comprises Medical Service Nodes(MSN) as $MSN = \{MSN_\alpha, MSN_\beta, \dots\}$. Only the HSPs mine the new blocks based on their reputation. However, the MSN nodes contribute to block verification together with the HSPs. We assume that each HSP and MSN has a digital certificate ($Cert_\alpha$) with the secret key (SK_α) and public key (PK_α) for the verification of the digital signature.

The proposed blockchain system facilitates the deployment of the medical sensor data validation framework VF_α such as [14], which is encoded as a smart contract. In addition, the system enables the deployment of several medical services functions MSF , such as [15] for diagnosis and [16] for data sharing, which correspond to the MSF specific privacy function PF encoded as a smart contract. The core components of the system are explained as follows.

1) *HSP*: uses the decentralization of smart contracts to verify the data locally according to the selected sensor data validation function VF for filtering out invalid data and to apply the

selected privacy function PF which corresponds to the medical service function MSF . The ledger stores the profile of the IoT sensor device D_δ connected to $HSP_\alpha Cert_\alpha$, and encoded smart contracts of verification function VF , the privacy function PF , and the medical service function MSF ,

2) *MSN*: leverages smart contracts to deliver the medical service functions MSF such as [15] for medical diagnosis with lower latency and improved scalability when compared with the cloud-based systems. The most important innovation is the ability to share the load of multiple medical service access requests of a centralized medical service among different MSNs.

3) *Medical IoT data verification function (VF)*: This function operates as a smart contract encoded with the logical specification to filter malicious data. For example, [14] performs range-based and time profile validation for filtering out malicious data.

4) *Medical Service Function (MSF)*: is the medical service facilitated by smart contracts. By incorporating smart contracts, the proposed system can act as a platform for multiple MSFs with reduced latency and improved scalability by eliminating the congestion of single-instance cloud-based medical ICT services. For example, privacy-preserved medical diagnosis service [15] is a potential MSF that can be continently integrated and deployed as a smart contract. In such integration, the risk of malicious data injection can be eliminated with the VF oriented reputation-driven IoT data formulation consensus mechanism, while achieving scalability through smart contracts. The patients can access the smart contract-based MSF deployed on the decentralized node, which is closer to the patients.

Encoding these VF and MSF functions as smart contracts increases the interoperability and scalability of the entire system, as multiple HSP nodes can receive, validate, apply different privacy functions, and store the data simultaneously without congestion as cloud-based services. At the same time, the $MSFs$ can process different medical ICT services with reduced latency as the requests are distributed across multiple $MSNs$. From a security perspective, the smart contracts provide an additional transparent layer of trust, rather than acting as a black box, and improved resistance to Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, while maintaining the on-chain integrity.

B. Adversarial model and security objective

In our work, we defined the threat model targeting three main adversarial instances as follows:

- Active adversaries that deliberately inject malicious data originating from IoT-integrated HSPs and eradicate the reliability of associated MSNs with malicious data-driven MSFs that emerge life-critical risks.
- Active adversaries that deliberately compete and attempt to surpass the previously mined nodes for dominating the mining power, bias the data, and reduce the fairness with the publicly available reputation score.
- Passive adversaries that observe the formulated medical IoT data in a plain form for adversarial insights, compromising privacy and compliance.

The main security objective is to design an IoT data formulation system that eliminates malicious data injection, and is robust to competitive miners that attempt to surpass the mining nodes for dominating mining power with preserved fairness.

C. End-to-end operational workflow

Algorithm 1 Inward data verification and privacy function smart contract

```

Require:  $\langle IR_\delta = D_\delta, d_i, Timestamp \rangle$ 
 $deviceProfile_\delta \leftarrow retrieveDeviceProfile(D_\delta)$ 
 $dataValidity \leftarrow verificationFunction(deviceProfile_\delta, x_i)$ 
if  $dataValidity == valid$  then
   $Priv_{BC}(d_i) \leftarrow privacyFunction(d_i, PF_\beta)$ 
   $Tx - Priv_r = \langle D_\delta, Enc_{BC}(d_i), PF_\alpha, UF_\gamma, Tstamp \rangle$ 
   $addToUnminedTxnPool([Enc_{BC}(d_i), Tstamp])$ 
else
  return  $invalidData$ 
end if

```

Algorithm 2 Reputation scoring and broadcasting smart contract - Mining node

```

Require:  $\langle Tx - Pool_j \rangle$ 
if  $currentState == miningState$  then
   $currentThreshold \leftarrow getThreshold(j - 1)$ 
   $Sc_{\alpha_j} \leftarrow generateReputationIndex(Tx - Pool_j)$ 
  while
  do
    if  $Sc_{\alpha_j} > currentThreshold$  then
       $candidateBlock_j \leftarrow formulateBlock(Tx - Pool_j)$ 
       $blockAddress_j \leftarrow storeBlock(candidateBlock_j)$ 
       $C_{sc} = r_{j1}G + sc_{\alpha_j}H \leftarrow generateComm(Sc_{\alpha_j})$ 
       $C_{Th} = r_{j2}G + Th_jH \leftarrow generateComm(Sc_{\alpha_j})$ 
       $broadcastBlock(Block_j, blockAddress_j, C_{sc}, C_{Th}, HSP_\alpha)$ 
      break;
    else
       $decrementThreshold()$ 
    end if
  wait( $waitingTime$ )
  end while
end if

```

Algorithm 3 Consensus smart contract - Other nodes

```

Require:  $\langle candidateBlockArray = [Block_j, DS - blockAddress_j, C_{sc}, C_{Th}, HSP_\alpha] \rangle$ 
 $maxHashBlock \leftarrow 0$ 
 $maxHashInt \leftarrow 0$ 
while  $i < length(candidateBlockArray)$  do
   $currentBlock \leftarrow candidateBlockArray_i$ 
   $currentBlockHash \leftarrow SHA256(C_{1i})$ 
   $currentBlockHashInt \leftarrow convertToInt(currentBlockHashInt)$ 
   $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
  if  $currentBlockHashInt > maxHashInt$  then
     $maxHashInt \leftarrow currentBlockHashInt$ 
     $maxHashBlock \leftarrow candidateBlockArray_i$ 
  end if
end while
 $Block_{max} \leftarrow maxHashBlock$ 
 $HSP_{max} \leftarrow maxHashBlock.minedNode$ 
if  $validateSignature(Block_{max}, HSP_{max}) == valid$  then
  if  $validateStorageHash(Block_{max})$  then
     $isReputationValid \leftarrow rangeProof(PedComm(Block_{max}.sc_j, PedComm(minedThreshold_v)))$ 
     $addBlockToLedger(Block_{max})$ 
  end if
end if

```

- 1) *HSP nodes send the sensor data to the blockchain:* The captured data element x_i from a sensor that corresponds to the parameter type $paramType$, D_δ , timestamp $Tstamp$ and the digital signature $digiSig_\delta$ is sent to the HSP blockchain node HSP_α as transaction Tx_δ such that,

$$Tx_\delta = \langle D_\delta, x_i, paramType, digiSig_\delta, Tstamp \rangle. \quad (1)$$
- 2) *HSP node verifies the sensor data:* The data validation smart contract of the HSP node validates the received data element x_i according to the VF (Eg. Range and time profile [14]).
- 3) *HSP node applies the privacy function on received data:* The HSP blockchain node applies the corresponding privacy function PF for the appropriate MSF (Eg. medical diagnosis use case online medical diagnosis [15]).
- 4) *HSP node checks the eligibility for mining:* The HSP node generates the reputation score and checks whether the node is qualified for mining. If qualified, the HSP node generates the Pedersen commitment for the proof and all nodes increment the threshold value parallel. If not all nodes decrement the threshold parallelly.
- 5) *Other nodes verify the reputation score for consensus:* Each blockchain node receives the mined block and verifies the qualifying condition of the valid block, whether the reputation score is greater than the threshold value, utilizing the BulletProofs protocol. If the block satisfies the condition, the block will be added to each member's ledger.
- 6) *Invoke medical service:* The MSN commit Tx_σ for medical service invocation, which is defined as

$$Tx_\sigma = \langle T_\theta, digiSig_\sigma, Tstamp \rangle. \quad (2)$$

that consists of the input $T_\theta = (t_1 \dots, t_m)$ for medical

Fig. 1: Proposed RepuChain architecture

Figure 1 shows the proposed architecture. The workflow of the proposal includes the following main steps.

Fig. 3: Experimental setup

an Intel(R) Core i5 -8250 CPU with four cores and eight logical processors. The entire implementation is based on the microservices architecture with Dockerized smart contracts and storage. The virtual machines used to implement the blockchain nodes are connected to the RabbitMQ messaging service for Pedersen commitment and block broadcasting in the consensus. We implemented the storage of the ledger with AeroSpike [17] distributed storage. BulletProofs Zero Knowledge Proof is implemented with open-source Java libraries. In the experiment, multi-threaded Java programs were used to simulate multi-scaled near-realistic transaction volume and evaluate the scalability. For experimental evaluation, the weight parameters of the Eq. (5) were set to $w_1 = 0.3, w_2 = 0.15, w_3 = 0.3$ with provisions to change in real deployments. Figure 3 shows the experimental setup used to evaluate the performance comparison of the proposed approach. In addition to our proposed work, we partially implemented the consensus mechanisms of [10] and [11] as they are respectively related to medical ICT services.

B. Mining node idled percentage comparisons

Decentralization is a key property expected in blockchain-based systems. In reputation-based consensus mechanisms, if limited criteria have been considered for reputation score evaluation, there is a tendency to converge the mining power towards a limited group, thereby reducing the data diversity and decentralization expectations. Technically, when the reputation scores of individual mining nodes are visible, the mining nodes can compete to increase the reputation by deliberately increasing mining qualifications such as stake [7]. Our work addresses these limitations in two directions. First, we propose a weighted and balanced multi-factor reputation mechanism as indicated in Equation 5, secondly with BulletProof [13] for hiding the reputation and obstruct competing without individual key generations [12]. For performance evaluation, we defined the mining node idled percentage as

$$r_{idledPercentage} = \frac{n_{idledNodes}}{n} \times 100\%, \quad (7)$$

and in this experiment, we programmatically instantiated a network of blockchain nodes to simulate a realistic environment of our work and [10]. The program generated random medical sensor data and forwarded them to our system and [10] to observe the evolution of both networks. The n indicates the number of nodes in the experimental environment, and $n_{idledNodes}$

indicates the number of nodes that were not elected to mine at least once during the experimental life cycle of the network, which is defined as idled nodes. Figure 4 reflects the results of the percentage of idle mining nodes in our method and the one in [10]. We found that our proposal performs much better compared to PoTE [10] with a lower percentage idled nodes, reflecting that the nodes in our work offer more mining choices than PoTE [10]. This clearly indicates more decentralization and reduced bias of the data towards a limited group. Our work provides more fairness compared to [10] and any other reputation score-based consensus, as our reputation score is based on weight-configurable multiple factors as Eq. (5). The results show that our work outperforms fairness with 97.4% mined node percentage compared to 7.7% of the state-of-the-art work of [10] (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Idled mining node percentage

C. Block mining duration comparison

In this experiment, we evaluated the average duration of a node's block mining lifecycle at different (unmined) transaction counts of a node. According to the core principles of blockchain, each node performs digital signature verification, the Merkle root, block header generation, and the addition of the miner's digital signature. In the PoW consensus mechanism as in [18], a mining node must prove a generated hash value for different leading number of zeros (difficulty level) corresponding to the block header, the unmined transactions and the nonce. In contrast, our work requires the reputation score proof that the mining node exceeds the current threshold in a mining session. We partially implemented TempChain [18]'s healthcare data-sharing process to evaluate the average duration of block mining for different leading zeros and the number of unmined transactions through programmatic tools with our work. The results in Figure 5 show that our work leads to a lower duration in block mining, indicating the latency advantage of our work. The numerical comparison between our proposal and TempChain [18] (with proof-of-work difficulty levels 5 and 6) shows significant improvements in the average block mining latency across all transaction levels. For example, at 500 transactions, our proposal achieves a latency of 2.0 ms, which is an improvement of 55.56% over TempChain [18] at difficulty level 6 (4.5 ms) and an improvement of 42.86% over TempChain

[18] at difficulty level 5 (3.5 ms). This trend continues at higher transaction levels. At 10000 transactions, our proposal's latency of 1.5 ms provides an improvement of 57.14% over TempChain at difficulty 6 (3.5 ms) and an improvement of 40.00% over difficulty 5 (2.5 ms).

From the results, RepuChain preserves fairness and reduces mining latency, reflecting the compatibility for scalable medical ICT systems. Finally, our work reduces computational costs in privacy-preserved reputation score proof as in [12] by integrating BulletProof [13]. Table I reflects a feature-wise comparison of our work with recent state of the art.

Fig. 5: Block mining duration - TempChain [18] vs RepuChain.

TABLE I: Features comparison with key related works

Features	[8], [10]	[6], [18]	[15]	Ours
Visibility of reputation to competitors	Yes	N/A	N/A	No
Proven fairness	No	No	No	Yes
Efficiency in mining	Yes	No	N/A	Yes
Multi instances of MSF	No	No	No	Yes

N/A : Not Applicable

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The digitalization of healthcare is expanding the possibilities of healthcare systems through the development of automated medical services. In parallel, reliable, fair, and unbiased data formulation is critical for life-critical medical IoT systems. Our work proposes *RepuChain*, a novel consensus protocol that ensures fairness and efficiency with a multi-parameter reputation score with the weighted contribution of data reliability evaluation and privacy-preserved reputation proof. The experimental results clearly reflect the fairness and efficiency advancement of *RepuChain* beyond state of art. In future, we expect to improve the consensus protocol by eliminating network and computational overheads for scalable medical IoT networks with improved security and efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was partly supported by 6G Flagship (Grant Number 369116) funded by the Research Council of Finland, European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under the Marie

Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 872752, ENSURE-6G project funded by the European Union (Grant ID. 101182933); CONFIDENTIAL-6G project funded by the European Union (Grant ID. 101096435); CONNECT phase 2 project by Research Ireland (Grant no. 13/RC/2077_P2).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Wang, G. Zhang, W. Wang, K. Zhang, and Y. Sheng, "Cloud-based intelligent self-diagnosis and department recommendation service using chinese medical bert," *Journal of Cloud Computing*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 4, 2021.
- [2] J. Park, D. H. Lee *et al.*, "Privacy Preserving k-nearest Neighbor for Medical Diagnosis in e-Health Cloud," *Journal of healthcare engineering*, vol. 2018, 2018.
- [3] J. W. de Kok, M. Á. A. de la Hoz, Y. de Jong, V. Brokke, P. W. Elbers, P. Thorat, A. Castillejo, T. Trenor, J. M. Castellano, A. E. Bronchalo *et al.*, "A guide to sharing open healthcare data under the general data protection regulation," *Scientific data*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 404, 2023.
- [4] A. Said, A. Yahyaoui, and T. Abdellatif, "Hipaa and gdpr compliance in iot healthcare systems," in *International conference on model and data engineering*. Springer, 2023, pp. 198–209.
- [5] K. Hameed, R. Naha, and F. Hameed, "Digital transformation for sustainable health and well-being: a review and future research directions," *Discover Sustainability*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 104, 2024.
- [6] A. Ekblaw, A. Azaria, J. D. Halamka, and A. Lippman, "A Case Study for Blockchain in Healthcare: "MedRec" Prototype for Electronic Health Records and Medical Research Data," in *Proceedings of IEEE open & big data conference*, vol. 13, 2016, p. 13.
- [7] R. Akkaoui, "Blockchain for the management of internet of things devices in the medical industry," *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, vol. 70, no. 8, pp. 2707–2718, 2021.
- [8] J. Yang, M. M. H. Onik, N.-Y. Lee, M. Ahmed, and C.-S. Kim, "Proof-of-Familiarity: A Privacy-Preserved Blockchain Scheme for Collaborative Medical Decision-Making," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 7, p. 1370, 2019.
- [9] M. M. H. Onik, S. Aich, J. Yang, C.-S. Kim, and H.-C. Kim, "Blockchain in Healthcare: Challenges and Solutions," in *Big data analytics for intelligent healthcare management*. Elsevier, 2019, pp. 197–226.
- [10] M. Z. U. Rahman, S. Akunuri, D. N. Babu, M. Ramprasad, S. M. Shareef, and M. D. Bayleyegn, "Proof of trust and expertise (pote): A novel consensus mechanism for enhanced security and scalability in electronic health record management," *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [11] A. Kumar and S. Jain, "Proof of game (pog): a proof of work (pow)'s extended consensus algorithm for healthcare application," in *International Conference on Innovative Computing and Communications: Proceedings of ICICC 2020, Volume 1*. Springer, 2021, pp. 23–36.
- [12] C. Huang, Y. Zhao, H. Chen, X. Wang, Q. Zhang, Y. Chen, H. Wang, and K.-Y. Lam, "zkrep: a privacy-preserving scheme for reputation-based blockchain system," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4330–4342, 2021.
- [13] B. Bünz, J. Bootle, D. Boneh, A. Poelstra, P. Wuille, and G. Maxwell, "Bulletproofs: Short proofs for Confidential Transactions and More," in *2018 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 315–334.
- [14] F. Hussain, S. G. Abbas, G. A. Shah, I. M. Pires, U. U. Fayyaz, F. Shahzad, N. M. Garcia, and E. Zdravevski, "A Framework for Malicious Traffic Detection in IoT Healthcare Environment," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 9, p. 3025, 2021.
- [15] D. Li, X. Liao, T. Xiang, J. Wu, and J. Le, "Privacy-preserving Self-serviced Medical Diagnosis Scheme based on Secure Multi-party Computation," *Computers & Security*, vol. 90, p. 101701, 2020.
- [16] M. Wang, Y. Guo, C. Zhang, C. Wang, H. Huang, and X. Jia, "Medshare: A privacy-preserving medical data sharing system by using blockchain," *IEEE Transactions on Services Computing*, 2021.
- [17] V. Srinivasan, B. Bulkowski, W.-L. Chu, S. Sayyaparaju, A. Gooding, R. Iyer, A. Shinde, and T. Lopatic, "Aerospike: Architecture of a Real-time operational DBMS," *Proceedings of the VLDB Endowment*, vol. 9, no. 13, pp. 1389–1400, 2016.
- [18] N. K. Dewangan and P. Chandrakar, "Tempchain: a blockchain scheme for telehealth data sharing between two blockchains using property mapping function," *The Journal of Supercomputing*, vol. 79, no. 13, pp. 14 808–14 826, 2023.